

The Effect of snap-off distance and screen variation on the screen-printed electrodes fabrication process

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ABSTRACT

Screen Printing Electrode (SPE) has advantages in production efficiency and cost opening up wider application opportunities in a wide range of industries, including medical, environmental, and sensor technology. In addition, the potential of SPE in detecting analytes with high sensitivity and selectivity can have a positive impact on the development of more sophisticated and accurate detection and monitoring systems. This research is carried out mechanically with a screen printing machine, so it is expected to get electrodes from screen printing that have better repeatability and sensitivity while the parameters used in the screen printing process are variations in setting the distance between the stencil and the substrate (snap-off) by 0.5mm; 1mm; and 1.5mm. Although made at low cost, electrodes for electrochemical biosensors have a fairly high repeatability percentage of 1.5-4.3%, so there is uniformity in prints using this machine.

Keywords: 3D electrodes, textured electrodes, screen printing method, high sensitivity, capacitive sensing

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INTRODUCTION

Technological developments in electrochemistry and sensory analysis have progressed rapidly [1]. Conventional electrodes consist of materials such as platinum, gold, or carbon but require complex and expensive processes to fabricate [2, 3]. In recent decades, the use of screen-printed electrodes (SPE) has become popular because of the advantages it offers [4]. The SPE manufacturing process is simpler and more efficient because it uses a screen printing technique, where conductive materials are printed on substrates with high precision and lower cost [5-7].

SPE's advantages in production efficiency and cost open up wider application opportunities in a wide range of industries, including medical, environmental, and sensor technology [8-10]. In addition, the potential of SPE in detecting analytes with high sensitivity and selectivity can have a positive impact on the development of more sophisticated and accurate detection and monitoring systems [11-14].

Based on previous research conducted by the author in 2020 with the theme of SPE fabrication and characterization using a T120 screen with variations in snap-off distances and layering numbers accompanied by the development of an SPE machine. According to the findings of the screen printing testing conducted using a machine-driven fabrication process, it has been

shown that the electrodes employed in electrochemical biosensors have a considerable degree of repeatability, specifically quantified at 2.6%. Through achieve cost-effective and streamlined production, the prints generated by this particular machine must exhibit a consistent level of uniformity in screen prints. [15].

For this research, it was carried out mechanically with a screen printing machine, so it is expected to get electrodes from screen printing that have better repeatability and sensitivity [16, 17]. The electrodes play a crucial role in facilitating signal transmission on electrochemical biosensors [18]. Diverse techniques can manufacture electrodes; however, a commonly employed method involves screen printing, which entails the integration of carbon-based conductive substances [19]. This approach is favored due to its cost-effectiveness, simplified fabrication procedures, and capacity for large-scale production. Conductive inks based on carbon and graphite are most often used due to their low price and good biocompatibility [20].

There is a demand for electrodes that possess enhanced sensitivity to facilitate expedited and precise detecting capabilities. To make these electrodes, regular 3 (three) dimensional textured electrodes are needed to capture cells well because the structure has good capacitive sensing.

RESEARCH METHODS

Tools and Materials

The tools used in this study were screen printing machines, digital balances, screen printing (T120; T150; and T180), squeegee (Unistar),

coater, OHP transparency mica plastic (Yashica), spatula, electric heating plate (Mingda Technology Co., Ltd.).

The materials used are conductive carbon ink (MJ Chemical), screen emulsion and sensitizer (photoxol 188), ethanol.

Figure 1. Screen Printing Electrode Machine

Screen Printed Electrode Fabrication Process

The FR4 substrate is positioned onto the SPE machine's surface, followed by a stencil on top of it. Next, the stencil is overlaid with commercial conductive carbon ink (MJ Chemical), and the application of carbon paste is facilitated by driving a squeegee (Unistar) using CNC code programmed with the Grbl controller software. The parameters employed in the screen printing process involve adjusting the distance between the stencil and the substrate (snap-off) by increments of 0.5mm, 1mm, and 1.5mm. The FR4 substrate, covered with conductive carbon ink in a specific pattern, is heated using an electric heater (Mingda Technology Co., Ltd.) at a temperature of 120°C for 5 minutes. [21-23].

Screen Printed Electrode Measurement

Geometric measurements conducted visually are facilitated using a digital microscope, namely the Dino-Lite model. Similarly, the examination of electrode surfaces and cross sections is accomplished by employing a digital microscope, also of the Dino-Lite variety. The Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) is a scientific instrument that

utilizes electron beams to produce high-resolution images of the surface of a sample. [24].

Electrical properties testing is carried out with the aim of determining the resistance value in the sample. Electrical properties were measured using LCR meters from STEMLab Red Pitaya with type 125-14.

The coefficient of variation is employed to quantify repeatability in measurement. The coefficient of variation is a statistical measure that quantifies the relative variability of a dataset by comparing the standard deviation to the mean. It is typically presented as a percentage. The coefficient of variation influences the quality of data distribution. If the coefficient of variation decreases, the data will exhibit greater homogeneity. Similarly, the data will display more significant heterogeneity if the correlation coefficient increases.

$$RSD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}{n-1}} \quad (1)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section consists of data from the results of dimensional analysis; observation of surfaces

and cross sections on electrodes based on the results of Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM);

measurement of electrical properties; and repeatability measurement.

Dimension Measurement

Figure 2. SPE Dimension Comparison Graph

Following the completion of the drying procedure, the solvent present in the carbon ink will undergo evaporation, forming a carbon layer on the substrate's surface. The electrodes were created based on test findings, incorporating modifications in snap-off distance characteristics. The outcomes of quantifying visual dimensions at each stage of screen printing production are depicted in Figure 2, as observed through a digital microscope.

product and design in the range of 51-167 μ m. The augmentation of distance snap-off induces a reduction in the thickness of the ink separation process, resulting in a decrease in the size of the ink deposited onto the substrate [25]. But on the T180 there is a contradiction where the SPE dimensions get bigger when the distance snap-off improved. Based on the graphical representation provided, it can be inferred that the utilization of T120 in screen printing results in a reduction in dimensional error of the electrode as the snap-off distance increases

Result from screen printing indicates the existence of manufacturing deviations between

Figure 3. Cross Section Measurement Chart for SPE

Based on the findings obtained through scanning electron microscopy (SEM) for each parameter, it is evident that the ink separation process exhibits a reduced thickness, resulting in a correspondingly diminished size of the ink particles deposited onto the substrate. But on the T180 there is still a contradiction where the results become greater as the snap-off distance increases.

Figure 4. Resistivity measurement graph for SPE

Measurement of Electrical Properties

The data taken is the resistance value of the specimen. The value is converted into resistivity value. Each pattern measured 3 (three) different specimens. This measurement aims to determine the resistivity value of the electrode specimen with different parameter variations.

With increasing effective surface area of the electrode, the amperometric current and voltammetry (i) or electrochemical flux are directly proportional to the actual electrode area. Corresponds to Figure 4 which shows the effect of surface area on the resistivity produced in each parameter.

Repeatability Measurement

For the results of screen printing on the SPE machine in Table 1 using the variation coefficient formula, in parameters with a snap-off distance of 0.5mm with the T120 mesh screen, the smallest variation coefficient is 1.5%, where the smaller the variation coefficient, the more homogeneous the data.

Table 1. Repeatability Calculation Results

Variable	T120			T150			T180		
	0,5	1	1,5	0,5	1	1,5	0,5	1	1,5
I	0,375	0,293	0,256	0,344	0,310	0,288	0,257	0,334	0,369
II	0,364	0,305	0,252	0,358	0,313	0,280	0,254	0,329	0,364
III	0,373	0,301	0,251	0,331	0,303	0,283	0,264	0,325	0,396
IV	0,354	0,301	0,247	0,349	0,313	0,274	0,282	0,343	0,394
STDV	0,010	0,005	0,004	0,011	0,005	0,006	0,013	0,008	0,016
Mean	0,367	0,300	0,251	0,346	0,310	0,281	0,264	0,333	0,381
RSD	0,026	0,017	0,015	0,032	0,016	0,020	0,048	0,023	0,043
%RSD	2,6	1,7	1,5	3,2	1,6	2,0	4,8	2,3	4,3

CONCLUSION

Deviation always occurs in every fabrication process using the screen printing method. The electrode fabrication process for electrochemical biosensors with the screen printing method produces increasingly stable geometric shapes, especially at electrodes with a snap-off distance of 1.5mm using the T120 mesh screen. The augmentation of snap-off distance will result in a decrease in the magnitude of the transverse cut area of the electrode. Using screen-printed electrodes in electrochemical detectors exhibits promising

prospects for advancement in electrochemical biosensor applications. Although made at low cost, electrodes for electrochemical biosensors have a fairly high repeatability percentage of 1.5-4.3%, so there is uniformity in prints using this machine.

To enhance comprehension regarding the optimization of print quality and the performance of Screen Printed Electrode (SPE) in printed materials, we can further examine the relationship between ink or carbon paste viscosity and screen printing quality because printing deviation may be affected by ink or paste viscosity and learn

more about the relationship between mesh tension and screen printing quality.

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